

Supplementary Materials

Table S1. Database search formulas (example for 4 databases)

PubMed	Search terms for query	Results
#1	“aging” (MeSH Terms) OR “aging” (All Fields) OR “ageing” (All Fields) OR “aged” (MeSH Terms) OR “aged” (All Fields) OR “older” (All Fields) OR “older people” (All Fields) OR “elderly” (MeSH Terms) OR “elderly” (All Fields) OR “older adults” (All Fields)	5,916,110
#2	“appetite” (MeSH Terms) OR “appetite” (All Fields)	47,371
#3	“energy intake*” (All Fields) OR “food intake*” (All Fields) OR “food intake*” (All Fields)	301,025
#4	“oral nutritional supplement*” OR “oral nutritional intervention*” OR “oral supplement*” OR “enriched meal*” OR “nutritional intervention*” OR “ONS”	95,371
#5	“anorexia” OR “anorexia of ageing” OR “elderly with anorexia” OR “older people with anorexia” OR “senile anorexia”	7,283
#6	“Randomized Controlled Trial*” [Publication Type] AND (“Randomized Controlled Trial*”[Title/Abstract] OR “randomization”[Title/Abstract])	152,454

#7	#1 AND #2 AND #3 AND #4 AND #5 AND #6	116
Embase		
#1	'anorexia of aging'/exp	1388
#2	'oral nutritional supplement*'/exp	10,017
#3	'older people':ti,ab,it OR 'older people'/exp OR 'older adult*':ti,ab,it OR 'older adult*'/exp OR elderly/exp OR elderly:ti,ab,it OR aged/exp OR aged:ti,ab,it	4,948,072
#4	'randomized controlled trial*':ti,ab,it OR 'randomization*':ti,ab,it OR 'randomized controlled trial*'/exp	948,576
#5	#1 AND #3	1,060
#6	#5 AND ([aged]/lim OR [very elderly]/lim)	589
#7	#6 AND #2 AND #4	101
The Cochrane library		
#1	MeSH descriptor: [anorexia of aging] explode all trees	81
#2	MeSH descriptor: [oral nutritional supplement*] explode all trees	2467
#3	Cochrane trials	1,728,081
#4	#1 AND #2 AND #3	6
China National Knowledge Infrastructure (CNKI) [Chinese]		
#1	'oral nutritional supplement*' (All Fields)	19

#2	aging” (All Fields) OR “ageing” (All Fields) OR “aged” (All Fields) OR “older” (All Fields) OR “older people” (All Fields) OR “elderly” (All Fields)	1986
#3	“anorexia of ageing” OR “elderly with anorexia” OR “older people with anorexia”	28
#4	#1 AND #2 AND #3	0

Table S2. Measurement of food and energy intake.

Study (author, year, country)	Measurement methods
Boudville, 2005, Australia	The amount of food stuffs consumed during each meal was determined and energy and macronutrient intakes were calculated using the Nuttab nutrient database (SERVE 3.95, SERVE Nutrition Management System, St Ives, New South Wales, Australia).
Ryan, 2004, France	All food and drink items (excluding water) were covertly weighed before and after each meal using standard electronic kitchen scales (accurate to 71 g). The corresponding energy (kJ) and macronutrient intake (g) of the amounts consumed, with and without the additional intake from the supplements, was calculated over the whole day using the meal analysis program Bilnut 4.0 (Nutrisoft, France).
Irvine, 2004, France	The weight of each food was recorded before and after meals using a Tefal kitchen scale (max 3 kg, precision 71 g). All items were weighed including snacks and drinks. Total energy intake was the sum of energy intakes for each meal plus snacks. Macronutrient and energy intakes were calculated from the weight of food consumed, the recipe used for cooking (available daily from the food production unit in hospital) and French food composition tables.
Faxen-Irving, 2011, Sweden	Total food and fluid intake was recorded at day 2-3 after admission, i.e., when the fat emulsion supplementation had started, and at day 8-9 or prior to discharge. The registration was performed by the staff by means of food records routinely used at the ward, i.e., the proportion of ingested food was estimated in quartiles in relation to the portion that was served. Fluid intake was estimated in ml.

Hubbard, 2008, United Kingdom	/
Pouyssegur, 2015, France	To compare the calorie supplement actually consumed from w0 to w6 between the two groups, dietary intakes were measured during 5 days (d0, d3, d6, d40 and d42). Food and beverage consumption was scored as the percentage of each serving actually consumed (score 0, 1/3, 2/3 and 1). In one nursing home, calorie count was done by the dietician in charge of the menus.
Gazzotti, 2003, Belgium	Consumption of each portion of supplement and regular meals were measured by direct observation and recorded as all, three quarters, half, one-quarter or none of the portion.
Stange, 2013, Germany	Food intake was recorded once, for 3 consecutive days, including 1 weekend day and 2 week days, 6 to 8 weeks after study start in participants of 5 of the 6 nursing homes. Trained research staff weighed and documented the amount of all foods offered and leftovers after the residents' meals and in-between meals, including ONS consumed on these days. Energy and nutrient intake was calculated using a nutrient-analyzing software (EbisPro Version 6.0; J.Erhardt, Stuttgart, Germany) which is based on the German Food Code (BLS II, 3).
Tylner, 2016, Sweden	To assess energy and nutrient intake (protein, calcium, and vitamin D) a 3-day food and fluid record was performed. The staff at each residential home was trained in how to register food and fluid intake. Any prescription or intake of nutritional supplements was also registered.
Smoliner, 2008, Germany	The nursing home staff was trained for dietary assessment, and food intake was recorded in standard portions. Single components of meals in addition to snacks and drinks were recorded. A research assistant visited the wards weekly to control recording of food intake. Energy and nutrient analyses were performed with

	EbisPro 6.0, which is based on the German food code.
Wouters-Wesseling, 2002, the Netherlands	<p>Before the intervention, food intake was assessed for three consecutive weekdays by a combination of weighed and unweighed dietary records by a trained dietician. The main meal was recorded by weighing the food if patients were served and by estimating portion sizes from standard measures if patients served themselves.</p> <p>Leftovers of meals were weighed or the proportion of the leftover in relation to standard measures was estimated. The intake from other meals during the day was a record in terms of current household measures and standard portion sizes reported by nursing staff.</p>
Brocker, 1994, France	Nutritional status was estimated on the basis of variables that were simple to measure in community practices.
De jong, 2000, the Netherlands	At baseline and in the last week of intervention, a 3 d (two weekdays and one weekend day; non-consecutive) estimated dietary record was collected by three trained dietitians. Food consumption data were coded (with a frequent cross-checking by all three dietitians) after which energy and nutrients were calculated with the computerized Dutch food composition tables (Stichting Nederlands Voedingsstoffenbestand, 1997). The energy and macronutrient content of the intervention food products were included in the food consumption data.
De jong, 1999, the Netherlands	Estimated dietary record was obtained by three trained dietitians at baseline (wk 0) and in the last week of intervention (wk 17). During a home visit before the intervention period, dietitians provided subjects with a clear explanation of the way to record and estimate portion sizes in household measures. During a second visit, they checked the diary and weighed the portion sizes of the most frequently consumed foods in household measures. Food consumption data were coded (with

	frequent cross-checking by all three dietitians), and energy and nutrients were calculated with the computerized Dutch Food Composition Table of 1997 and a supplement (1995) for folate and vitamin B-12 (Stichting Nederlands Voedingsstoffenbestand 1995 and 1997).
Faxen-Irving, 2002, Sweden	/
Carlsson, 2005, Sweden	A dietary assessment was done by asking questions about the minimum daily intake of certain food items, chosen as important contributors of energy or other nutrients. The dietitian made an estimate of a normal day's food consumption. The nutritional value of the ONS was included in the calculation of the dietary intake at 6 months. Intakes were calculated by a standardized software program: Kost & Näringsdata AB, Dietistprogram, Stockholm, Sweden (The Swedish National Food Administration, 2000).
Olin, 2008, Sweden	Two methods were used for registration of the food intake. The first was a 24-hour recall the residents were asked to recall the type and amount of all food and fluid consumed at each eating occasion the previous day and night. The 24-hour recall was used as a checklist for a one-day estimated dietary record, which was performed within a few days after the recall. The investigators registered the food and fluid intake at all eating occasions during one day. A telephone call was made to those residents who stayed up late in the evening to inquire about any additional intake.

Table S3. Characteristics of the measurement of subjective appetite in the included studies

Study (author, year)	Tools	Points	Assess method	Assess time	Assess content	Additional content
Brocker, 1994	VAS	0-100	/	/	validated 100-point VAS (Comparisons between scores given by the various practitioners / could not be made because each treated only 10 patients).	
Irvine, 2004	VAS	/	/	VAS was completed every half hour from before breakfast until lunch and hourly thereafter until diner. A total of 10.5 h was monitored. One investigator (PI) measured the lines with a ruler, to the nearest mm.	Questionnaires consisted of an A4 sheet of paper with seven 100 mm lines corresponding to seven questions considering hunger, fullness, desire to eat, pre-occupation with food, thirst, stress and cold. Weighted at the end of each line were two extreme states in relation to the question asked. The two answers	Desire to eat, a psychological rather than a physical sensation, referred to their earning for some food, differing from “preoccupation with food” which was termed as an inability to think of

					anchoring each end were “not at all” and “extremely”. Patients were instructed to mark a point on the line between the two extremities that best described their sensation.	anything else but food. Fullness (used proxy measure of satiety) was evaluated by the question “How full do you feel” and described as the pleasant state of contentment felt after eating.
Boudville, 2005	LS	five-point	The subjects completed.	On four occasions immediately before and 10 min after the pre-meal drinks and immediately before and after the meals.	to assess hunger, thirst, fullness, prospective consumption (“how much they could eat”) and nausea.	/
Pouyssegur, 2015	NS	0-10	Rated by the participant or by the nursing staff.	from w0 to w6	0 (absolutely no appetite) to 10 (extremely good appetite)	

Carlsson, 2005	VAS	0-3	An experienced hospital dietitian (PC) made a 20–30 min long interview of the patients about their appetite and food habits (the week before the fracture) on the second post-operative day and 6 months later at the outpatient department.	on the second post-operative day and 6 months later at the outpatient department.	The patients rated their appetite: 0=good appetite, 1=neither good nor poor appetite, 2=poor appetite but eating, 3=poor appetite and not eating. The patients described if their meals were self made and, by using familiar household measures, the size and composition of their meals.	Executive personal: an experienced hospital dietitian (PC).
Faxen-Irving, 2011	VAS	0-10	Performed with the support of the study nurses (3 nurses)	Before lunch at first day of inclusion and at day 8 after inclusion.	Five questions were given, considered to evaluate various aspects of appetite, i.e., hunger and desire to eat. The questions were: 1. How hungry do you feel? 2. How full do you feel? 3.	The patients in the intervention group were asked to rate the acceptance of the product on a scale ranging from 0 to 7,

					How strong is your desire to eat? 4. How much do you think you could eat now? 5. How preoccupied are you with thoughts of food?	higher values indicating better acceptance.
Tylner, 2016	VAS	0-10	Were asked to rate their appetite.	All assessments and blood samples were performed and collected at start and end of each study period.	/	/
de Jong, 2000	LS	/	/	/	After reading the question, subjects had to score on a point LS with verbally labelled answering categories. An example of a question is the following statement: In former days my appetite was: 1. much better than nowadays, 2. better than nowadays, 3. the same as nowadays, 4. worse than	A higher score corresponded to a more positive feeling about their taste and smell perception, a better appetite and more feelings of hunger. Initially variables were calculated: present

nowadays, 5. much worse than
nowadays.

taste perception
(eight items, range
8±40), present smell
perception (three
items, range 3±15),
appetite (six items,
range 6±30), daily
feelings of hunger
(nine items, range
9±45), present smell
perception compared
with the past (three
items, range 3±15).

VAS: visual rating scale; LS: Likert Scales; NS: Numerical Scale.

Table S4. Converted values included in the meta-analysis of appetite

Study (author, year)	ONS			Control			Time	Points
	mean	SD	n	mean	SD	n		
Brocker, 1994	0.44	0.18	92	0.38	0.21	93	30d	0-100
Brocker, 1994	0.62	0.19	92	0.47	0.23	93	60d	
de Jong, 2000	-0.167	0.133	40	0	0.2	36	/	0-10
Faxen-Irving, 2011	0.64	2.8	24	-0.56	2.9	27	/	0-10
Pouyssegur, 2015	0.443	0.719	61	0.151	0.601	51	w0 to w6	0-10
Pouyssegur, 2015	0.611	0.763	54	0.2	0.639	50	w0 to w10	0-10
Pouyssegur, 2015	0.784	0.832	51	0.191	0.741	47	w0 to w18	0-10